

**Wetland
Mitigation Banking
program**

Offsetting for payment for
ecosystem services

CLIMATEFIT International best
practice factsheet

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Summary

The Wetland Mitigation Banking Program (WMBP), managed by the U.S. Department of Agriculture's Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS), is designed to support agricultural producers who need to offset their negative impacts due to regulatory compliance requirements. This program has been operational since 2014 and facilitates the establishment of wetland mitigation banks, which are crucial for farmers needing to drain wetlands for agricultural use while maintaining compliance with environmental regulations. These banks provide participating producers with an efficient mechanism for mitigating lost wetlands.

WMBP is a market-driven approach where farmers purchase credits from mitigation banks to offset the environmental impact of draining wetlands. This setup allows for the balancing of agricultural productivity and environmental preservation. The program's success depends on its ability to provide a streamlined solution for farmers to continue their agricultural operations without compromising environmental standards. By purchasing credits, farmers can adhere to compliance regulations and maintain eligibility for other USDA benefits. This approach not only supports sustainable agricultural practices but also promotes the restoration and preservation of wetland ecosystems, contributing to broader environmental objectives such as flood control, habitat protection, and water quality improvement.

Keywords: wetland, mitigation banks, farmers, regulators

Actor(s) interviewed: Official at NRCS.

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Further reading: [Wetland Mitigation Banking Program](#)

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Best practice information card

Table 1. Wetland Mitigation Banking Program. Information card

Location	United States of America
Population size	335 million
Project area size	NA
Area type	Rural, wetland
Climate challenge	Wetland loss is accelerated by climate change and leads to significant biodiversity loss as these critical ecosystems are degraded or submerged. This destruction disrupts habitats for numerous species, undermining ecological balance and resilience.
Key Community System(s)	Ecosystem and nature-based solutions, land use and food systems, water management
Objectives	The Wetland Mitigation Banking program aims to achieve the no net loss of wetlands due to agricultural practices. Farmers are driven to destroy wetland areas in their lands because they can cause hindrance to their activities and reduce profitability. This program helps farmers comply with wetland conservation regulations and ensures that overall wetland health is maintained.
Climate challenge solution	The WBMP program enables the farmers who are looking to offset their negative impact to purchase credits from established mitigation banks. These credits represent ecologically restored wetlands elsewhere and compensate for the lost wetland.
Key benefits	The WBMP program benefits both farmers and the environment. Farmers can comply with wetland conservation regulations by purchasing credits from mitigation banks, avoiding costly on-site mitigation projects. This program also helps maintain overall wetland health by creating new wetlands to compensate for those lost to agriculture.
Implementation status	2014 to present
Investment volume (€)	Initial funding- 10 million USD, current funding- 5 million USD per year
Key financing barriers	NA
Financial model	The Wetland Mitigation Banking Program (WBMP) aims to achieve no net loss of wetlands due to agricultural activities. It does this by enabling farmers to mitigate wetland impacts on their land. Farmers achieve mitigation by purchasing credits from established mitigation banks. These credits represent ecologically restored wetlands elsewhere, compensating for the lost wetland functions on the farmer's property.
Financial sources	Public- National government (Grants) Private- Households- property owners
Financial instruments	Results based financing- Payment of Ecosystem Services Fee/User charges: Offsetting

Overview and timeline

The Wetland Mitigation Banking Program (WMBP) is a program managed by the United States Department of Agriculture. It is a competitive grants program that supports the development and establishment of wetland mitigation banks to make credits available for agricultural producers. It is designed to help farmers who have small, temporary, and seasonal wetlands that they wish to drain so they can farm in the area. For example, if there is a small muddy wetland in the middle of a field, a farmer who drains that wetland without any correspondence with the USDA risks jeopardizing their USDA benefits, such as crop insurance, price support payments, and disaster payments. Farmers facing this situation can purchase credits at a mitigation bank to offset the environmental impact of draining the wetland.

The Wetland Mitigation Banking Program is administered by the Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) and offers a market-based approach to wetland mitigation. Credits typically function on an acre-for-acre basis. When a farmer's agricultural activities require the draining of a wetland, they can purchase credits from an approved mitigation bank to compensate for the ecological impact. The NRCS provides financial assistance through grants to establish these banks, but the operations of the banks are managed by third-party entities. These entities determine the credit price based on market factors, independent of government involvement. This market-driven pricing structure incentivizes private investment in wetland restoration and creation, making it an attractive option for both mitigation bank operators and farmers.

There is a broader Wetland Mitigation Program in the US that also focuses on other developers besides agricultural ones. **This report, however, focuses on the Wetland Mitigation Banking Program operated and administered by the NRCS, specifically targeting agricultural producers and offsite mitigation.**

The WMBP prioritizes the creation of mitigation banks for smaller, temporary, and seasonal wetlands, typically under five acres (2 hectares) in size. This focus aligns with the program's target beneficiaries: agricultural producers. Unlike some wetland mitigation programs used for government infrastructure projects, this program only supports farmers who need to drain wetlands incompatible with their operations.

The WMBP strictly limits credits to agricultural producers seeking to mitigate the impact of draining small wetlands incompatible with their farming operations. These wetlands often disrupt field layouts and hinder machinery use. Program participation hinges on adherence to conservation compliance regulations, which prohibit wetland conversion for crop production. Before the NRCS approves the farmer to destroy the wetland and mitigate it, the farmer must prove that it was inevitable. Following that, they also have to show how they tried to minimize the unavoidable impact.

Figure 1. Example of small wetland in a field that can disrupt agricultural activities Source: NRCS

Oversight of Mitigation banks: The NRCS prioritizes applications for establishing wetland mitigation banks based on project location, the experience of the applicant, potential benefits to historically underserved producers, and shovel-readiness (the ability to begin restoration immediately upon receiving funding). **Once awarded, the NRCS provides technical oversight throughout the bank's lifespan. A core component of this oversight is the mitigation banking instrument, a detailed document outlining the bank's operation.** This document provides specifics on wetland restoration plans, site locations, long-term maintenance strategies (in perpetuity), credit determination methods, and metrics for assessing restoration success. The document also addresses contingencies like bank bankruptcy and includes financial assurances to ensure continued site maintenance in such scenarios. The approved mitigation bank entity becomes responsible for securing sites, developing the draft banking instrument, and submitting it for NRCS review. The mitigation banks are also required to submit quarterly project reports to keep the NRCS informed on progress and any emerging concerns.

Figure 2. Restored wetland under the WBMP of the NRCS. Source: NRCS

The WBMP emerged because of the widespread recognition of the critical ecological services provided by wetlands. These services include flood control in upper watersheds by retaining peak floodwaters, providing vital habitats for migratory waterfowl, and contributing to water quality by filtering nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus runoff before they reach rivers and streams. Recognizing these significant benefits, both government and public stakeholders, including environmental groups, citizens, and community organizations, prioritized wetland conservation.

Farmers recognized the need for a program like the WBMP specifically for the agricultural sector. The U.S. Army Corps of Engineers had established a successful mitigation banking program for large-scale development projects (roads, housing, commerce) with regulations already in place. Recognizing its potential benefits, agricultural stakeholders requested a tailored program to address wetland mitigation challenges faced by farmers.

Finding sites for wetland restoration is the biggest barrier for this program. The WBMP has to find sites that were historically drained before 1985, which is not always easy. Therefore, finding easy-to-restore sites to create the banks is one of the biggest challenges of the program. The WBMP originated with farmers in the Prairie Pothole Region (North Dakota, South Dakota, Iowa, and Minnesota). These states have significant small wetlands, which can hinder agricultural expansion. **Farmers from these regions lobbied their Congressional representatives, and the program was incorporated into the 2014 Farm Bill.**

The program has a two-part legal framework. Mitigation banks that want to establish or restore wetlands have the option to apply for additional funding through a government grant application process. This application includes an easement deed¹, which guarantees perpetual wetland maintenance. A separate legal agreement is then signed between the mitigation bank and farmers purchasing credits. This agreement serves as a binding contract for wetland mitigation services.

Wetland protection is a mandatory condition for agricultural producers to maintain eligibility for USDA benefits programs. These programs include disaster payments in the event of natural disasters and subsidized crop insurance, which significantly reduces crop loss risk for farmers. The USDA covers approximately two-thirds of crop insurance costs, and the farmers pay the remaining one-third. If farmers want to have access to these USDA benefits, they have to adhere to the wetland conservation regulations (which include offsetting negative impacts) and implement erosion control practices on highly erodible land.

Table 2. Wetland Mitigation Banking Program. Timeline with key moments

Date	Key moment
Early 1980s	Wetland mitigation banking is first introduced in the US
1987	The US includes no net loss as a major goal for national wetland policy. The US No Net Loss policy aims to achieve overall no net loss of wetlands acreage and functions. This means any unavoidable wetland losses from development projects must be balanced by creating, restoring, or enhancing wetlands elsewhere.
2014	Farmers successfully lobby lawmakers to create a wetland mitigation banking strategy specifically for agricultural producers and it is included in the 2014 Farm Bill

¹ A deed is a legal document granting rights to a specific property. An easement deed allows a party that is not the owner to use a portion of the land. It is a written agreement between two parties that spells out what part of the property is available for access and how it may be used. Source: [Courthouse direct](#)

Governance and key stakeholders

Figure 3 displays the organizational structure of and the key stakeholders involved in the The WBMP. **The Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS)** is the regulator of the entire process and provides technical oversight, grant administration support, and program guidance. The NRCS is also responsible for moderating any conflicts that might arise. They approve all mitigation banks and also approve applications by farmers. In addition they also provide minimum deed terms for conservation easements protecting land that is part of a WBMP project. The NRCS also certifies the credits, though they do not determine the price of each credit.

Figure 3. Governance and key stakeholders of WBMP. Source: author

Private mitigation banks are established and managed typically by specialist ecological restoration companies, play a crucial role. These companies have the expertise required to restore wetlands and replace their ecological functions, for other sectors as well, not just other sectors. They must identify and secure sites and customers without NRCS help. They also need to submit regular project reports and communicate any concerns or issues to the NRCS. The mitigation banks also determine the price of each credit that can then be negotiated by farmers.

Farmers that want to mitigate wetland impacts represent the third stakeholder group. They purchase credits from approved mitigation banks to offset their environmental impact.

In the entire process, first private companies must establish mitigation banks through initial wetland restoration and establish credit reserves. Once these restored wetlands have been approved by the NRCS, farmers can purchase credits from the bank to offset the ecological impact of their wetland conversion activities. This streamlined approach allows farmers to comply with regulations by making a single financial transaction with the bank.

Mitigation banks use a NRCS approved functional assessment procedure to determine the number of available credits for each restored bank site.

Table 3. Wetland Mitigation Banking Program. Key stakeholders and their responsibilities or roles

Stakeholder	Type	Role and responsibilities
NRCS	Public	Regulator of the process, oversees all functions and approves all applications, resolves conflicts when they arise
Mitigation Banks	Private	specialist ecological restoration companies, establish and restore wetlands and generate and sell credits to farmers
Farmers	Private	purchase credits from approved mitigation banks to offset their environmental impact

Business model & financial model

Business model

It is important to note that wetland mitigation banks are not physical locations that need to be built from scratch. Essentially, **mitigation banks are mechanisms that allow for the enhancement and restoration of wetlands to compensate for unavoidable wetland losses elsewhere due to farming activities.** First, ecological companies that want to sell credits have to find a degraded wetland or another location that has the potential to be restored or enhanced. This process can involve analyzing land use maps, aerial photographs, and conducting on-site evaluations. Once the site is chosen, the ecological companies must get the mitigation bank approved by the NRCS. They can also apply for additional funding through grant allocations after their application has been approved. The final step involves selling the mitigation credits to farmers who need to compensate for wetland losses. The mitigation bank itself is the program that facilitates the search for and creation of offsetting possibilities. Finding sites for restoration is a crucial initial step in establishing a functional mitigation bank.

Mitigation banks under the WBMP of the NRCS are for the exclusive use of agricultural producers who need to comply with wetland conservation provisions. Credit buyers must be USDA program participants who need credits for mitigating small, temporary, and seasonal wetlands. Funds cannot be used for construction, i.e., Clean Water Act mitigation.

The NRCS uses a wetland assessment methodology to evaluate both the sites to be drained and the potential restored wetland sites, assigning scores that reflect the ecological functions replaced by mitigation. This evaluation is done before the transaction between the farmers and the banks takes place. The mitigation banking instrument document outlines details of bank site restoration. Ideal sites are those with minimal past disturbance. Restoration typically involves filling drainage ditches to allow natural hydrology to return and re-establish native vegetation through the existing seed bank.

To maintain eligibility for most USDA programs, farmers must comply with certain conservation provisions. Related to wetlands conservation compliance, farmers may not plant an agricultural commodity on a converted wetland or convert a wetland to make possible the production of an agricultural commodity. Priority is given to banks based in locations with significant numbers of individual wetlands, wetland acres, and conservation compliance requests. According to NRCS data, these locations include the Prairie Pothole Region, the Nebraska Rainwater Basin Region, and the states of Iowa, Nebraska, Michigan, Minnesota, Wisconsin, Indiana, Illinois, South Dakota, Georgia, and Ohio.

The program was established in 2014 through farm bill legislation with an initial 4-year pilot funding of 10 million USD. Due to its popularity, it has continued beyond the initial four-year period. **The current annual funding of the program is 5 million USD.** This funding is provided to the NRCS specifically to run this program. The staff at the NRCS who oversee the program are a small team. The NRCS partners with third-party entities and private companies with wetland expertise to establish and manage mitigation banks. **A large portion of the 5 million USD is also used to give grants to these private companies that need additional resources to establish mitigation banks. Grants range from 400,000 USD to 1 million USD, and priority is given to applications from historically underserved groups and those located in regions with high farmer demand for wetland mitigation.** There is a matching requirement of 25% of the federal grant that is provided. This means that if a mitigation bank applies for 1,000,000 USD in funding, they have to commit to funding at least 250,000 USD, making the total project cost 1,250,000 USD. Generally, expenses required from mitigation banks are also eligible to be used as matches. Mitigation banks can also include unrecovered indirect costs and costs associated with easement acquisition when applying for grants. While farmers ultimately pay mitigation banks to offset wetland impacts through credit purchases, the program also utilizes a cost-share approach for mitigation bank establishment through the cost-matching requirement.

Officials at the NRCS do not have access to the price of each credit or any other financial transactions that take place in this program. This information remains between the farmers and the mitigation banks. Information such as the location of mitigation banks and GIS data is protected and not publicly available.

The program prioritizes mitigation within the same hydrologic unit code (HUC) as the impacted wetland. HUCs are geographic areas defined by drainage patterns, with smaller codes representing larger watersheds. This regional focus ensures that the restored wetland in the mitigation bank is ecologically similar to the impacted wetland. They should have similar characteristics such as size, type, plant and animal communities, and overall functions to the replaced ecosystems. The mitigation banks should ideally be placed near the ones that are being impacted. For example, a drained depressional pond wetland would be mitigated by the restoration of another depressional pond wetland within the same HUC.

The NRCS uses part of its 5 million USD for program administration and technical expertise requirements. A portion of this funding is used for government staff within each state who oversee and assist mitigation banks. The cost of implementing the program is not expected to go down since the cost of farmland is increasing. This rising land value is a significant factor influencing agricultural producers' decisions to drain or modify

wetlands, as these areas represent potentially profitable cropland. The program has to balance agricultural needs with wetland conservation efforts in the context of a growing population and increasing food production demands. Following appropriation and review of program funds, the NRCS announces grant opportunities through Grants.gov, allowing eligible entities to apply for funding to establish mitigation banks.

The NRCS uses the following criteria to determine whether private mitigation banks qualify for grant funding or not:

- All required documents present (incomplete applications may be disqualified without further review for missing information)
- Geographic scope: within the priority area or not
- Project Goals: are the goals clear, measurable and achievable?
- Project Management: how much expertise does the team have?
- Historically underserved outreach (producers and potential bank sites)
- Bank Development and Operation: specific plan; priority to "shovel ready" projects

The approved mitigation bank entity becomes responsible for securing sites, developing the draft banking instrument, and submitting it for NRCS review. The mitigation banks are also required to submit quarterly project reports to keep the NRCS informed on progress and any emerging concerns.

The NRCS can only see the applications after they have been submitted through their portal, so banks are encouraged to go through their website carefully and ask questions before submitting the application.

Figure 4. Example of grant application submitted to the NRCS. Source: NRCS

After a mitigation bank has been established, the government matches the banks with farmers that want to offset their impact. A separate legal agreement is then signed between the mitigation bank and farmers purchasing credits. This agreement serves as a binding contract for wetland mitigation services.

The NRCS also uses a WBMP instrument document that gives specifics on wetland restoration plans, site locations, long-term maintenance strategies (in perpetuity), credit determination methods, and metrics for assessing restoration success.

It also includes guidelines on the following:

- Baseline Information
- Site Protection
- Determination of Credits
- Performance Standards
- Financial Assurances
- Long Term Monitoring and Maintenance

Wetland mitigation banking offers several climate benefits. Wetlands act as natural sponges, storing water during wet periods and releasing it slowly during dry periods. This helps mitigate drought conditions by maintaining groundwater levels, which are crucial for irrigated agriculture in states like Nebraska and Iowa. Additionally, wetlands contribute to climate change mitigation through significant carbon sequestration. The plant communities within wetlands absorb substantial amounts of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere.

Ultimately, successful wetland restoration benefits everyone: the environment gains vital ecological functions, local communities see improved well-being, and future generations inherit a healthier planet.

Financial model

The WBMP can be interpreted as a form of Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) instrument. PES schemes² are market-based instruments that aim to compensate landowners or managers for providing ecosystem services. These services are the benefits humans derive from nature, such as clean water, flood control, carbon sequestration, or biodiversity. PES schemes offer a promising approach to promoting sustainable land management and environmental conservation by creating a market for the valuable services provided by healthy ecosystems.

Wetland mitigation banking also focuses on ecosystem functions provided by wetlands and aims to provide a compensatory mechanism for any loss of wetlands. Like many PES schemes, the WBMP operates on a market-based approach. The credits that are created represent the ecological value of restored wetlands. Farmers who need to compensate for wetland loss can purchase these credits from the bank, creating a financial incentive for wetland restoration and conservation. One aspect in which the WBMP differs from traditional PES schemes is that while PES generally rewards landowners for managing their land for conservation, the WBMP primarily functions as a compliance tool. Farmers are required to mitigate their wetland losses; otherwise, they will lose their USDA benefits.

In traditional PES schemes, providers of ecosystem services receive direct payments from beneficiaries. However, in the WBMP, the payment comes indirectly. The bank profits from selling credits, not from receiving direct payments for restored ecosystem services. Overall, wetland mitigation banking can be seen as a market-based, compliance-driven form of PES that focuses on compensating for lost wetland functions through the restoration of wetlands elsewhere. **In one year, the NRCS typically provides grant funding to 5-10 mitigation banks. Following that, any other financial transactions take place between the farmers and the mitigation banks, with the NRCS taking a regulatory role (see Figure 5).**

²Payments for environmental services (also known as payments for ecosystem services or PES), are payments to farmers or landowners who have agreed to take certain actions to manage their land or watersheds to provide an ecological service. As the payments provide incentives to land owners and managers, PES is a market-based mechanism, similar to subsidies and taxes, to encourage the conservation of natural resources. Source: [International Institute for Environment and Development](#)

Figure 5. Financial transactions in WBMP. Source: author

If a mitigation bank receives a grant from the NRCS, the funds acquired can be used for the following:

- Development of the mitigation banking instrument.
- Identification of suitable mitigation sites and performance of functional assessments to determine the available credits and a credit release schedule.
- Market research and contracting for mitigation activities.
- Land surveys, permitting, and title searches.
- Design and formulation of mitigation plans.
- Restoration, enhancement, or creation of wetland mitigation bank sites in accordance with NRCS conservation practice standards.
- Tracking and management of wetland mitigation data.
- Direct administrative costs associated with implementing the project.
- Indirect costs

It cannot be used for the following purposes:

- Purchase of land or conservation easements
- Capital expenditures for general purpose equipment, buildings, and land and for improvements to land, buildings, or equipment which materially increase their value or useful life.
- Expenses already funded through another program

Farmers who use the WBMP are attracted to the streamlined solutions to their negative impacts. Traditionally, farmers would be required to undertake on-site mitigation efforts by replicating the destroyed wetland somewhere else on their property. This can be expensive, time-consuming, and doesn't always achieve the desired ecological outcomes. Mitigation banks provide farmers with the opportunity to purchase credits from pre-established wetland restoration projects. These credits represent quantifiable units of ecological value generated by the bank's restoration activities. However, the credits do not transfer the ownership of a specific portion of the restored wetland. This financial contribution from developers helps to offset the costs associated with wetland restoration, ultimately leading to a net ecological benefit. The ownership of the banks is private. Ecological companies (who run the mitigation banks) either pay the owners of these sites or share a percentage of credit sales with them. The owners of these wetlands are also typically farmers. In some cases, mitigation banks buy the site. The restored wetlands are never on public lands.

The wetland mitigation credit transaction process uses a well-defined protocol. First, the NRCS conducts a site evaluation and issues a certified wetland determination, verifying the presence and quantifying the acreage of a wetland on the farmer's land. The farmer then presents this certification to a mitigation bank and requests the purchase of wetland credits equivalent to the impacted wetland area. After the credit purchase, the mitigation bank issues a transaction form, which documents the transfer of credits to the farmer. This form is submitted to the NRCS, along with the certified wetland determination, as verification of mitigation completion. Finally, the NRCS updates its records to show the mitigated wetland impact.

Enabling conditions

The following factors have enabled the implementation of the wetland mitigation banking program in the US:

- **Experienced Professionals:** The program relies on specialists in ecological restoration, both within the private sector (mitigation banks) and government agencies (biologists overseeing mitigation efforts).
- **Cost-Sharing Mechanisms:** To address upfront costs, the program utilizes a cost-share approach. Mitigation banks contribute a portion of project funding and government agencies can allocate resources to support staff overseeing the banks.
- **Regulatory Framework:** Wetland mitigation banking operates within a well-defined legal framework which is the Clean Water Act. It is implemented through federal regulations and mandates compensatory mitigation for wetland impacts if they are destroyed through agricultural activities. This creates a demand for mitigation credits that the private sector can provide.
- **Government Oversight:** The NRCS has an important role in overseeing mitigation banks.

The program also actively mitigates risks through open communication. Frequent dialogue happens between NRCS staff, mitigation banks, and farmers. Regional NRCS staff travel to meet with mitigation banks to discuss challenges and then develop solutions. Additionally, the NRCS prioritizes outreach efforts in states lacking established mitigation banks to address geographic coverage gaps and improve accessibility for farmers.

Wetland mitigation banking relies on collaboration between several groups, all having different contracts. Private environmental consultants might be hired by mitigation banks to navigate the permitting process and even help set up the bank itself. These consultants act as intermediaries, adjusting and negotiating agreements between the bank and other parties. Landowners and farmers can also get involved by forming joint ventures with mitigation bankers, essentially sharing profits from credit sales. Lawyers are involved to draft these contracts and resolve any disagreements that might arise. These are all standard, comprehensive agreements.

Outcomes

The program's cost-share requirement, where mitigation banks contribute a portion of project funding, was initially a small hurdle. However, the mitigation banks have generally found solutions to this problem. For example, some large companies contribute by utilizing their own equipment for project development. In Iowa, a successful strategy involved the mitigation bank hiring a marketing firm to promote the program and demonstrate alternative methods for satisfying the cost-share element.

The program is also considered to be very cost-effective from the NRCS's point of view. The funding is used effectively, as the responsibility of restoring and maintaining wetlands has been shifted to private entities, reducing the burden on the government. Data on the number of credits traded, financial transactions, and the price of each credit are not publicly available.

The main beneficiaries of the program are the farmers and the mitigation banks themselves. The program also has wider societal benefits from wetlands, along with reduced public expenses for wetland restoration. For mitigation banks, the biggest issue they face is securing suitable restoration sites. Certain wetland types, such as linear wetlands in Nebraska, are very desirable for irrigated agricultural expansion but are particularly difficult to locate. Additionally, encountering endangered species during site assessments can significantly delay projects due to consultations with the Fish and Wildlife Service.

The interviewee for this case highlighted that the WBMP has bipartisan support. Changes in federal administration over the past decade have not shifted or decreased funding for this program. Environmental groups have been positive toward the program's contribution to wetland restoration and protection efforts. Farmers are generally happy with the streamlined mitigation process by the NRCS and the mitigation banks. This consensus on the program's benefits has contributed to its ongoing stability. The NRCS estimates that the program will remain funded in the coming years since it is smoothly run and provides tangible benefits. The number of banks has also increased in recent years as the demand for credits has risen.

Lessons learned

Successes and limitations

The following section is derived from the interview.

One major limitation that the program faces is that sometimes farmers have to undertake activities that are outside the scope of the WBMP. WBMP targets small and low-level wetlands. If a farmer wants to drain a semi-permanent or a large wetland on their field, that is outside the scope of the program, and they are not permitted to drain the wetland in such cases.

High upfront costs can also be a possible hindrance for small farmers with limited resources. Purchasing credits from mitigation banks can be expensive. Increasing land prices can exacerbate this challenge, impacting the viability of establishing new banks and limiting affordability for farmers. Additionally, rising land prices may also constrain the number of grants that the NRCS can provide per year.

In addition, WBMP primarily addresses compensatory mitigation for agricultural impacts, not broader wetland restoration goals. This focus can neglect opportunities for wetland enhancement or proactive conservation efforts beyond offsetting negative impacts to maintain farmers' eligibility for USDA benefits.

One challenge highlighted in the interview is staff turnover at NRCS, which can impact the effectiveness of the WBMP. Biologists involved in the program initially may retire or move to other government agencies, necessitating the NRCS to recruit additional experienced staff. The NRCS employs a team-based approach for conflict resolution. Since the program's inception, several conflicts have arisen. For example, environmental groups raised concerns about potential negative impacts of a mitigation bank site on endangered whooping cranes. The NRCS addressed this by relocating the planned mitigation bank site.

Another recurring conflict involves the language used within perpetual wetland easement deeds required for mitigation banks. These deeds define permitted land uses, such as mowing and vegetation management, and activities that could degrade the wetland, like snowmobiling. The NRCS is developing a standardized easement deed template to streamline approval processes and minimize conflicts arising from easement language.

The perpetual wetland easement deed requirement presents a procedural hurdle for mitigation banks. The legal language within these easements must undergo thorough review and approval by government lawyers before filing. The standardized easement deed template that the NRCS is developing aims to streamline this process. It will be included in future grant announcements, providing mitigation banks with a pre-approved legal framework to facilitate easement establishment.

A significant risk for farmers in the WBMP is the limited availability of mitigation banks in their vicinity. Some states lack any mitigation banks, requiring farmers seeking to offset their impact to look for mitigation banks in other states.

Transferability conditions and potential

The most important factor for successful program implementation by NRCS is having experienced ecological restoration specialists in the private sector (the mitigation banks), along with government staff who possess expertise in wetland mitigation. For any jurisdictions interested in implementing similar strategies, it is crucial to assess the availability of ecological companies in the area capable of providing services like mitigation banking.

NRCS receives \$5 million USD in funding, a significant portion of which is allocated to grants. Streamlining the grant process can make programs like these cost-efficient and alleviate any burden on local governments, with NRCS assuming a regulatory role.

It is also essential for jurisdictions to maintain comprehensive records of ecological areas. NRCS utilizes a GIS layer encompassing all wetlands within its territories, enabling effective monitoring and compliance enforcement. Wetland compliance is breached when a farmer drains their wetland without notifying NRCS. For a first violation, they are given one year to restore the wetland and mitigate its negative impact. Repeated violations may result in the loss of the wetland and other USDA benefits. To streamline processes, jurisdictions are advised to develop standardized procedures, including templates for easement deeds and documents related to wetland compliance.

Related factsheets

The WBMP model shares similarities with the EcoMarkets (ID04), Groenfonds (ID06) and Edwards Aquifer Protection Program (ID20).

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